

P-ISSN: 3046-7519
E-ISSN: 3032-4920

OPEN ACCESS

Journal of Aceh Studies (JOAS)

www.journal.institutre.org

JOURNAL OF ACEH STUDIES (JOAS)

The multidisciplinary journal of Aceh society

P-ISSN: 3046-7519 | E-ISSN: 3032-4920 | Journal homepage: <https://journal.institutre.org/index.php/joas>

The Acehese Literature and Social Behavior

Fitriya Munidar
University of Gothenburg

Abstract

This research essay analyzes the relationship between Acehese literature and social behavior. Writing in Acehese has served as a vehicle for contemplating Aceh's political and human conditions, particularly in the aftermath of the tsunami and post-conflict periods. With data from sociolinguistic analysis, netnography interviews, and literature evaluations, the study used a descriptive qualitative research approach. The results demonstrate that reading Acehese literature can be seen as both a cultural battle within the reading community and a vehicle for political purification and introspection. Along with these language variations, the study looks at slang, idiolect, dialect, and acrolectal in both North and West Acehese. According to the report, there are active Acehese groups in Malaysia that participate in social events, such as celebrating Islamic holidays. The survey also indicated that the use of local language in public spaces like as coffee shops is still less desirable amongst youth in Aceh. The study comes to the conclusion that social behavior and cultural identity are strongly correlated with Acehese language and literature.

Keyword: Aceh, Literature, Behavior, Social, Culture

* Corresponding author, email: fitriamunidharg@gmail.com

Received 24 November 2023; Received in revised form 20 July 2023; Accepted 24 July 2023; Available online 01 January 2024

© Published by Journal of Society Innovation and Development. This is an open access article under the CC BY-SA 4.0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>).

INTRODUCTION

Aceh is a region in Indonesia that has experienced long-term conflict and natural disasters such as earthquakes and tsunamis (Lee-Koo, K, 2015). These situations have affected the social behavior of Acehnese people and have been reflected in Acehnese literature (Gaillard, J., Clavé, E., Vibert, O., A., D., Denain, J., Efendi, Y., Grancher, D., Liamzon, C., Sari, D., & Setiawan, R, 2008). Acehnese literature has been used as a medium to reflect on the humanity and political situation in Aceh, especially in post-conflict and tsunami situations. This scientific article aims to explore the relationship between Acehnese literature and social behavior, including language varieties, social identity, and cultural values (Kasim, F., & Nurdin, A, 2021).

METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative research design, with data sources from literature reviews, netnography interviews, and sociolinguistic analysis. The literature review explores the relationship between Acehnese literature and social behavior, including the use of Acehnese literature as a medium for contemplation and a tool for political cleansing. The netnography interviews explore the identity of Acehnese people in the commercial diaspora of grocery stores in Malaysia, including their social activities and cultural values. The sociolinguistic analysis explores the varieties of language in North Acehnese and West Acehnese, including idiolect, dialect, acrolectal, and slang.

The data sources for this study include academic journals and research articles that explore the relationship between Acehnese literature and social behavior. The data sources also include netnography interviews with Acehnese people who live or have a grocery store in Malaysia, as well as sociolinguistic analysis of the varieties of language in North Acehnese and West Acehnese.

The data analysis for this study is descriptive in nature. The results of the data analysis are presented descriptively, including the findings that Acehnese literature can be viewed as a medium for contemplation and a tool for political cleansing, as well as a cultural struggle among the reading community. The study also found that Acehnese communities in Malaysia are active in carrying out social activities, including commemorating Islamic holidays. The study also found that the use of local language in public spaces such as coffee shops is still less preferable amongst youth in Aceh.

FINDING

The findings of this study show that Acehnese literature and language are closely related to social behavior and cultural identity. Acehnese literature has been used as a medium to reflect on the humanity and political situation in Aceh, especially in post-conflict and tsunami situations. Acehnese literature can be viewed as a medium for contemplation and a tool for political cleansing, as well as a cultural struggle among the reading community. Acehnese communities in Malaysia are active in carrying out social activities, including commemorating Islamic holidays. The use of local language in public spaces such as coffee shops is still less preferable amongst youth in Aceh (Sofyan, z., & Jafar, A, 2021).

DISCUSSION

The discussion of this study highlights the importance of Acehnese literature and language in shaping social behavior and cultural identity. Acehnese literature has been used as a medium to reflect on the humanity and political situation in Aceh, and it can be viewed as a tool for political cleansing and a cultural struggle among the reading community. The study also highlights the importance of preserving local language and cultural values, especially in the face of globalization and modernization. The study suggests that Acehnese literature and language can be used as a means to promote social harmony and cultural diversity (Sahlan, M., Fajarni, S., Ikramatoun, S., Kamil, A., & Ilham, I, 2019).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this scientific article explores the relationship between Acehese literature and social behavior, including language varieties, social identity, and cultural values. The study finds that Acehese literature and language are closely related to social behavior and cultural identity. Acehese literature has been used as a medium to reflect on the humanity and political situation in Aceh, and it can be viewed as a tool for political cleansing and a cultural struggle among the reading community. The study suggests that Acehese literature and language can be used as a means to promote social harmony and cultural diversity.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Gaillard, J., Clavé, E., Vibert, O., A., D., Denain, J., Efendi, Y., Grancher, D., Liamzon, C., Sari, D., & Setiawan, R. (2008). Ethnic groups' response to the 26 December 2004 earthquake and tsunami in Aceh, Indonesia. *Natural Hazards*, 47, 17-38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11069-007-9193-3>.
- Lee-Koo, K. (2015). Marjaana Jauhola. Post-Tsunami Reconstruction in Indonesia: Negotiating Normativity through Gender Mainstreaming in Aceh. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 17, 185 - 186. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2014.987496>.
- Tabacco, G. (2018). "When I saw the elephants": extraction of minerals and gendered precariousness in the Acehese landscapes. , 5, 97-112. <https://doi.org/10.14672/ADA2018138997-112>.
- Kasim, F., & Nurdin, A. (2021). Religion as a Social Capital in Realizing Disaster Resilience in Aceh. . <https://doi.org/10.2991/ASSEHR.K.210125.037>.
- Mujib, I., Abdullah, I., & Nugroho, H. (2013). "ISLAM" IN THE GLOBAL VILLAGE: Post-Tsunami Dialog and Negotiation of Aceh Identity. *Al-Albab*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.24260/ALALBAB.V2I2.37>.
- Wahid, U. (2013). THE FUNCTION OF MEUNASAH IN SOCIAL CULTURAL COMMUNICATION PROCESS WITHIN ACEHNESS SOCIETY. *Journal of Human Capital Development*, 6, 151-167.
- sofyan, z., & Jafar, A. (2021). HIKAYAT 'ANEUK YATIM' (Kajian Sosiologi Sastra Melalui Pendekatan Dialektika). , 23, 119-135. <https://doi.org/10.22373/ADABIYA.V23I1.9036>.
- Hafnidar, H., Junita, N., & Ratna, R. (2017). A Study on the Forgiveness Concept of Aceh Conflict Victims. , 7, 849. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0007097403160320>.
- Sahlan, M., Fajarni, S., Ikramatoun, S., Kamil, A., & Ilham, I. (2019). The Roles of Ulama in the process of Post-Conflict Reconciliation in Aceh. *Society*, 7, 251-267. <https://doi.org/10.33019/society.v7i2.106>.
- Adji, A. (2011). SOCIAL ECONOMIC INTEGRATION IN ACEH: PRIOR-POST TSUNAMI. , 14, 51-62. <https://doi.org/10.14203/widyariset.14.1.2011.51-62>.